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IMPACT OF RESOURCE CONTROL AGITATIONS AND INSTITUTIONAL AGENCIES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NIGER - DELTA REGION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: Resource Control Agitation, otherwise known as the resource Control Movement, has been a topic of debate since the late 1990s over the control of oil resources in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. The people of the Niger Delta have been agitating that since Nigeria receives 95% of its foreign exchange from oil should have a fair share from the proceeds of oil sales for the development of the Niger Delta. The researcher adopted a descriptive survey design for the study. Sample size of 320 respondents drawn from the entire population of the study area was used. Frequency tables were used to ascertain the number of occurrences of phenomena of interest. The Pearson product correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between Niger Delta agencies and the development of the region. Resource curse theory propounded by Richard Auty in 1993 was anchored as the theoretical foundation for the study. The following findings were made from the analysis. The major challenge bedevils the development of the Niger Delta region is corruption among elites and agencies. There is poor implementation of several policy frameworks enacted by the federal government in addressing Niger Delta region development issues. The Niger Delta elites are not effectively involved by the resource control agitator in the region, thus making it seem like gangsterism demands from government institutions. The study concludes that the legal regimes and institutions /commissions established over the years and the manipulation of the same arising from the conspiracy of the elites within and outside the region are the major obstacles to the agitation for resource control by the people of the NDR. The study recommends that resource control agitations should eschew violence and armed struggle and engage their past and current governors to give account of their stewardship vis-à-vis the political/ establishment group in the struggle; to join hands with other stakeholders for the call to restructure Nigeria to reflect on true federalism.

Keywords: Resource Control, Institutional Agencies, Niger Delta Region, Development, Commissions.

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Introduction

The rationale behind the steady and constant agitation and struggle in the Niger Delta area is a result of long-lasting suffering, penury, and difficulties experienced by the people in the region due to activities surrounding oil exploration and abandonment of the region (Abodunrin, 2019 in Oyinlola, 2021). The origin of the Niger Delta is associated with agitation. For resource control. Akoh and Okonmah (2009) posit that “resource control struggle emerged after the abolition of slave trade in 1807”. Indigenous merchants engaged in resource control struggles to actively participate in the palm oil business. Consequently, resource control was one of the factors showcasing Niger Delta representation in the Willink Commission’s inquiry into the reasons. For minorities to accommodate them in 1957 (Ako & Akonmah, 2009). Resource control struggles were first championed by Issac Adaka Boro in the post-crude oil era in his efforts to establish the NDR in 1966. This marked the beginning of youth restiveness in the Niger Delta due to oil-related derivations in the region. Human Right Watch Africa (1999) posits that the Niger Delta representatives could not realize their aim to carved out Nigeria as an independent entity or even legalize it its own. This spurred the struggle. For resource control, which has been suffering a series of setbacks. The struggle was smooth and peaceful in the early 1999 until the Ogonis wandered into the struggle and it escalated in militancy and violence, with arm and other supplicated weapons applied. Ukeje (2011) contends that “the response of the federal government has typically included the creation of development boards, state creation, agencies, pacification and more recently the amnesty initiative and the creation of Ministry of Delta Affairs”. The Niger Delta agitation’s failure is proportionately hinged on the Federal Government and oil major’s activities due to policy summersaults. The government spending a huge sum of Naira in little payments, educational, and vocational training of ex-militants sparked a strong sentiment among the people that the government has not invested resources to cushion the effect of the agitation for resource control. Thus, no visible success has been recorded in agitation so far. The nexus between resource control and true federalism is hinged on the derivation principle, which entails restructuring Nigeria to reflect each region’s equity and fairness. Egobueze et al. (2020) contend that “the pre-occupation of the theory of fiscal federalism is to answer the fundamental questions of the rationale for adopting federalism in a country and the rules for the assignment of functions and sources of revenue to different levels of government.”. This raised strong ululations of the people of the Niger Delta because the oil from which Nigeria gets 95% of its foreign exchange is located on their land. It is their right to get their fair share of the proceeds of oil sales to develop their area”. Ekuri and Etim (2017) assert that the present resource control mechanism apart from the fiscal federalism policy in the First Republic is not only controversial but also patently skewed in favor of the federal government even when the government has not shown a bitter way of investing the huge allocations it gets from controlling our Nigerians”. Succinctly, the people could not enjoy any reasonable or meaningful benefit from their God-gifted wealth, land and agricultural source of livelihood due to the poor development of their area. Federal government efforts to respond to the yearnings of the people established boards, agencies, and programs and ministries to bring development closer to the people, but it is not enough to relax the tempo of the struggle of the Niger Delta people. The southern geopolitical region of Nigeria is the location of the Niger Delta people. It has 7.5% of the land mass cutting across about 70,000 km². The area has a boundary with the south through the Atlantic Ocean and the Republic of Cameroon. It also shared a boundary through the west by Ogun, Oyo, and Kogi States, north by- Benue State, and in the eastern part of Nigeria. The area is composed of 11 states, including Abia, Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, and Edo, Imo, Ondo, and Rivers. The population of the Nger Delta area is estimated at 31 million people. The region consists of 40 ethnic groups with over 250 different languages, and they are predominantly agrarian in nature. They live on lowland

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and mangrove areas. Hemen and Ngwoke (2021) averred that "Nigeria was the world's highest exporter of cocoa, the country had a viable agro-economy spanning from the groundnut pyramids, beans and millet of the north and cocoa, oil palm, coal and fish of the south, which portrays the exact economy of the Niger Delta people." This paper seeks to examine the nexus between the Niger Delta agitation for resource control and the institutional challenges bedeviled the development of the area, as well as to provide recommendations and solutions to be adopted by various authorities and people in the Niger Delta region.

Statement of the problem

The major debate rocking among non-oil producing states that oil belongs to Nigeria and not to the Niger Delta alone is evidently manifested in the approaches employed by the Nigerian government and other institutional agencies concerned. The consensus opinion of the South West, South East, North, and other geopolitical zones shows that the government should maintain the status quo in the utilization of oil wells continuing to produce the bedrock of the Nigerian economy. The federal government asserts that based on the structure of Nigerian federalism, it will create more to cater, for more than any state. The burden in Exclusive Lists still permits the federal government to majorly contribute in managing the welfare and development of its citizens in the 36 federation states including FCT, Abuja. Moreover, granting Niger Delta agitation may bring perpetual economic dwindling and hardship to the entire country. This snowballed the Niger Delta people into uncontrollable vexation and injustice, which they continue to hold that the federal government willfully refuses to develop the region instead of implementing marshaled plans, as was the case in Europe at the end of 2nd World War. The contradictions inherent in the legal framework of the policies and program initiated by the federal government have graciously abrogated the Niger Delta people's objectives. Therefore, institutional mechanisms, legal regimes, and elite conspiracy be the bane of the struggle. For resource control and development in the Niger Delta. The broad objective of the study is to examine the effects of resource control agitation on the development of the Niger Delta region. Other specific objectives of the study include: (a) determining the extent to which legal regimes have militated against the struggle for resource control in the region, (b) establishing the nexus between the institutions and agencies in addressing the developmental challenges of the Niger Delta region and (c) ascertaining if the elites within and outside the region are partners in crime in frustrating all the developmental giant strides meant for the region and efforts of the resource control agitators in the region.

Literature Review

Many scholars have not compromised on the given exact conceptualization of resource control in the Nigerian context. Reboots and Oladeji (2005) contends that "while one group conceives it as the total takeover of the resources located in the resource producing states by the people of those states, others see it as the stakeholders in the resource owned area should manage a greater proportion of the resources harnessed in those areas". Henryik (2009) conceived resource control as the "control and management of resources by State or Local Governments that have jurisdiction over the extraction of resources". From the above, federal government guidelines on environmental control maintain that state or local governments should manage and control resources within their areas, but in partnership with the tier of government that has superlative oversight. Ofeimum (2005) cited Dickson and Asua (2016) and opined that resource control is the principle that permits every federating unit to be empowered. For self-government. This refers to the self determination of people within their area. Dickson and Asua (2016) asserted that resources control is the "way and manner the government revenue is shared among the various tiers of government the Federal State and Local Governments, as well as how resources available are harnessed and determined". Again, Ya'u (2001) asserts that resource control may mean the "substantive power for the community to collect monetary and other benefits accruing from the exploration, exploitation and use of

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resources in their domain and deploy same to its developmental purpose” (Dickson and Asua, 2016). Azaiki (2003) viewed it as the nexus between resource control and federalism a basic economic theory that postulates that lands, labor, capital, and entrepreneurship are factors of production within the context of federalism. This means that the federating units within the federal government have the right to control the natural resources within their borders with an agreed contribution toward maintaining a common service at the center. Similarly, Adesopo and Asaju (2004) see resource control as the “right to control or manage the revenue accruing from oil and other natural resources in line with the tenets of true federalism”. This shows that resource control is the same true federation. Ako (2011) reported that the above analogy emphasizes fiscal federalism because the federating units manage and control resources within their territory. It was still obvious that “resources producing areas ought to have control over resources located in their areas, with minimal intervention from the federal government, as it is the practice in the United States of America, Canada, and Switzerland, amongst others (Ekuri, & Etim, 2017)”. On the contrary, the above conceptualization is not reflective of federalism applicable in Nigeria. This is because in a real sense, Nigeria is in common with unitary federalism in practice.

Niger Delta Institutions Resource Control Agitations

In every present-day society, the social engineering tool law this is because it portrays the relationship between the umpire and its citizens. Even from the time of colonia administration, law has been used to control land and; resources (human and materials) to avoid anarchy. The Land Use Act 1978 vested ownership of land in the state permits the appropriation of land for any oil-related activities with possible payment of due compensation to the concerns. It was on this premise that the Niger Delta people go range in the agitation of the resource control in their area at any slightest provocation Ako (2012) asserted that “the constitution regulates the relationship between the federating units and the federal government in the same way the legal framework regulating Nigeria’s oil industry which is the fundamental cause of the resource control-orchestrated restiveness in the region” It could be deduced that the Constitution and other existing laws are the challenges to the realization of recourse control agitation from the NDR. Ako (2012) posits that “irrespective of the four broad classes of resource control being advocated for, amendment to the extant legal framework is necessary”. Nwankwo et al (2021) maintained that “in order to meet the aspirations of the South-South region, the Nigerian government created OMPADEC (presently known as NDDC) and allocated to them 13% of oil derivation in favor of oil-producing states outside monthly allocation from the federation account”. To put an end to Niger Delta agitation, the ministry Niger Delta was also created with the mandate of proposing a lasting and satisfactory revenue allocation formula capable of quenching agitation in the country. The Niger Delta continues to feel marginalized due to the absence of development in the area.

Stakeholders in the Struggle for Niger Delta Resource Control

Niger Delta position

The people of the Niger Delta believed in maintaining total and principal resource control in their area. Ako (2011) points out two broad notions of resource control :(a) “Absolute resource control”. And (b) principal resource control and increased derivation. He is saying that proponents of ‘absolute’ resource control take the stance proffered at Kaiama Declaration saying that every region should control its resources 100% to maintain the notion of absolutism, the various militant groups in Niger Delta integrated to form one group known as MEND. The MEND marked the movement of violence in the agitation of resource control in the Niger Delta region. On the other hand, “the advocates of principal resource control see it as Niger Delta having a direct and decisive role in the exploration, exploitation and disposal sales of the oil” (Sagay, 2001)”. Dafinone (2001) posits that the governors of southern states made a silly mistake in referring to the notion of true federalism in the

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discourse of resource control of their land in Nigeria. It is the argument of the Niger Delta that the federal government, the oil majors, and the Nigerian elites have enriched themselves immensely while the oil owners are dying of hunger, poverty, no developmental projects in their area. Akumagba (2002) argued that “Principal resource control thus the desire of every state in the federation of Nigeria to control and manage the natural resources located therein... we do not want to seize the oil, but to participate”. Aluko (2012) argued that “while the political class have shown irresponsibility in the management of accruing oil revenues to state coffers, the militants enjoy the reward of their struggle with monthly stipends from the government and vocational and educational training opportunities to the exclusion of these ordinary citizens who’s on behalf of political and militant agitation has taken worst dimension”.

Non-oil-producing States (NOPS)

It is not an overstatement to say that the non-oil-producing states concurred that Nigeria is wholly dependent on the oil-producing states (Niger Delta). For survival. The 36 states survive monthly on the allocation from the federation account. Salaries, schools, roads, and other infrastructural development cannot be undertaken by any state without government allocation. However, out of the selfish interest of the non-oil producing states argued that it will be out of proportion more derivation is allocated monthly to Niger Delta that it reduces their general allocation. It is an injustice on the Niger Delta people whose livelihood has been destroyed by oil spills. Their standard of living became ordinary. The slogan of the non-oil-producing States,” oil belongs not only to the Niger Delta but also to Nigerians” eluded their mentality to forget the extent of Niger Delta suffering on their land. It is a pity. The National Political Reform Conference argued that the upward review of the 13% derivation to 25% offshore/onshore dichotomy debate was a welcomed epoch in enhancing the development of the NDR. The irksome part of the non-producing areas was that meeting the demands of the Niger Delta people would have an adverse effect on the political economy of the non-oil producing areas. In the same vein, Sagay (2002) posits that the “attitude of the non-oil producing states toward the plight of the coastal states, during the hearing of the resource control case was unsympathetic and hostile”. One can rightly state that “most of the non-oil producing states simply plunged their knives into the already open and bleeding wounds of the Southern minority of the Niger Delta” (Egugbo, 2016”.

Federal Government

The federal government has been contending that its position between oil-producing and non-oil-producing states is inconveniencing the government economically because both depend on the monthly pay from the federation account. For survival. Oil belongs to the Nigerian government and, as such, needs to be shared based on the principles of equity, fairness, and justice between the federal government and oil-producing and non-oil-producing states. The federal government, being the oil landlord, need to take the lion’s share of the resources due to multiple responsibilities bequeathed on it. Perhaps, it is the duty of the federal government to cater and provide essential services to the citizenry. The legal control on the generation and, exploitation of all natural resources enables her to allocate revenues to the federating units. Egugbo (2016) referred to the “case of offshore/onshore dichotomy in which the Supreme Court entered judgment in favor of the FG on April 5, 2001.” Resources control agitation was mainly championed by the elites from south-south geopolitical zone in Nigeria. Okolo and Akpokighe (2014) report that the “position of the Northern elites on the demand for resource control was found in an article captioned States Cannot Control Resources read in The Punch Newspaper on April 6, 2001 where Alh Umar Tukur Dangaladima dismisses the demand as unrealistic, adding that the Niger Delta people only settled there and inherited the resources and cannot claim ownership talk more of control. However,

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all these arguments are overruled by the stance that the government owns land and the resources in it. Issues concerning oil are handled by the federal government as referred to in exclusive list of the Nigeria constitution.

Resource Control Groups in the Niger Delta

Many administrations in Nigeria have failed to provide lasting panacea to provide the developmental challenges of the Niger Delta area, despite the 13% revenue derivation from which the elites conspired to make selfish wealth. (Agudiegwu & Ezeani, 2017). When the MEND group took violent approach, several other groups rose from their slumber to attack old majors and the federal government alleging their responsibility. For misfortunes over resource control. The groups were later stratified into the following groups:

Environmental/Ecological group: This group pursues the effect of oil spillage and population in their land environment. Lobbying the federal government to provide funds to cushion the effects of environmental degradation due to the economic hardship it has caused on their people.

Political/Establishment group: This group comprise national and, local politicians, stakeholders, chiefs, business men from Niger Delta area. They influence debates in favor of resource control agitation. For their people. They seek to ensure that a Niger Delta man is appointed as the CEO of the NNDC commission and ministry of Niger Delta. This is the most selfish group because they are self -financial gain-oriented.

The Militant Group: Just as their name implies. The group consists of gangers, street boys, and men of desperados. They felt that since negotiation and dialogue failed, there was need to cause wreckages, aiding and abating oil bunkering, gangsterism, and arm proliferations as the only means to make money in sustaining and redeeming their economic difficulties. Hemen and Ngwuoke (2011) suggested that Nigeria should adopt a hybrid ownership system in which the State (both federal and federating States) and individual landholders own petroleum resources in Nigeria against the activities of this group.

Theoretical Framework

The theory considered suitable for this study is the resource curse theory. Richard Auty propounded the theory in 1993. The theory holds that country with large natural resources may be unable to use them to boast economic development and, as such, will have lower economic growth than countries without rich natural deposits. The struggle over who gets the lion's share of the natural resource causes economic stagnation, conflicts, corruption, and environmental degradation. The theory states that a nation with abundant natural resources will experience poor economic growth and negative social outcomes if they are not well controlled. The resource curse theory is also known as the paradox of surplus. However, to me, it should be referred to as a mirage of abundance, owing to the fact that you have enough that one expects to cater for your needs, but you end up being a pauper, which is "dreamless hope in a hapless circle". This is because there is a low development outcome as Niger Delta people expected development in both human and material, but the reverse became the case. To respond to the welfare of the people manifested into the corruption of the elites who created multiple militant groups that are causing the conflict in the Niger Delta resource control agitation. Institutional agencies become more corrupt by siphoning the sumptuous funds that the federal government has allocated to the region to enhance the development of the area. This brought about a higher wave of conflict, authoritarianism, and low economic stability in the Niger Delta region compared to the development and economic growth experienced by the non-oil-producing states in Nigeria. Okpebenyo et al, (2023) posit that the possession of natural resources is a desirable succor. For both some states and the Niger Delta people. Regrettably, the expected benefits of such resources are far from being realized because of external factors such as poor governance, corruption, and lack of accountability. The relevance of the theory to the study hinges on unveiling the root cause of the Niger Delta resource control agitation crisis in Nigeria, which stems from the government's ability to provide for the people, the institutional agencies' corrupt

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practices manning the affairs of the Niger Delta people, and the elites’ unguarded conduct who collaborated with youths to form different militant groups that revolted against the federal government. The factors constituted the non-achievable reality of the Niger Delta people’s objective of controlling the resource in their domain.

Methodology

To realize the stated objective, the researcher adopted the descriptive survey method. The primary source of data was used, whereas secondary sources of data were employed to complement the information required as documentary evidence. These include journals, magazines, periodicals, magazines, workshop/seminars, bulletins, and e-library materials. The information generated from the sources was used by the researchers to achieve the stated objective. The population of the study comprised all the institutions/agencies selected from 6 states drawn from the NDR which is 971,844 according to the 2006 census. Using the Taro Yameni formula, Frequency tables were used to determine the number of phenomena of interest. The Pearson product correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between Niger Delta agencies and the region’s development.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + \frac{N(e)^2}{N}}$$

Where; n = desired sample size
 N = total population
 E = acceptable error limit (0.05)²
 N = 971,844
 $= \frac{971,844}{1 + 971,844(0.05)^2}$
 $= \frac{971,844}{1 + 971,844 - 0.025}$
 $= \frac{971,844}{+ 2429.61}$
 $= \frac{971,844}{2430.61}$
 $= 320.83$
 $= 320$

The researcher used Bowley’s Proportional Allocation Formular because of the various state agencies under review.

The proportional allocation formular is given as

$$nh = \frac{nNh}{N}$$

Where; nh = number allocated to each local government area
 n = total sample size;
 NhNh = total population of each local
 N= total study population

The calculation table is shown below.

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Questionnaire allocation per state

S/N	Name of the states	Population	Sample size	Calculation	Questionnaire allocation
1.	Cross River	149,683	320	$\frac{149683}{971,844} \times 320$	49
2.	Akwa Ibom	195,55	320	$\frac{195555}{971,844} \times 320$	64
3.	River	214,969	320	$\frac{214,969}{971,844} \times 320$	72
4.	Edo	133,625	320	$\frac{133,625}{971,844} \times 320$	44
5.	Delta	156,649	320	$\frac{156649}{971,844} \times 320$	52
6.	Ondo	121,363	320	$\frac{121363}{971,844} \times 320$	39
	TOTAL	971,844			320

Source: Survey of the researcher. 2025

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE RESPONSES

Frequency Table

VAR00001

		Frequency	Percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative
Valid	HE	99	30.9	30.9	30.9
	LE	75	23.4	23.4	54.4
	ME	77	24.1	24.1	78.4
	VHE	28	8.8	8.8	87.2
	VLE	41	12.8	12.8	100.0
	Total	320	100.0	100.0	

VAR00002

		Frequency	percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	HE	103	32.2	32.2	32.2
	LE	74	23.1	23.1	55.3
	ME	39	12.2	12.2	67.5
	VHE	69	21.6	21.6	89.1
	VL	1	.3	.3	89.4

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	VLE	34	10.6	10.6	100.0
	Total	320	100.0	100.0	

VAR00003

		Frequency	percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	HE	53	16.6	16.6	16.6
	LE	76	23.8	23.8	40.3
	ME	49	15.3	15.3	55.6
	VHE	97	30.3	30.3	85.9
	VLE	45	14.1	14.1	100.0
	Total	320	100.0	100.0	

VAR00004

		Frequency	percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	H	3	.9	.9	.9
	HE	61	19.1	19.1	20.0
	LE	24	7.5	7.5	27.5
	ME	48	15.0	15.0	42.5
	VHE	143	44.7	44.7	87.2
	VLE	41	12.8	12.8	100.0
	Total	320	100.0	100.0	

VAR00005

		Frequency	percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	He	6	1.9	1.9	1.9
	HE	42	13.1	13.1	15.0
	L	9	2.8	2.8	17.8
	LE	49	15.3	15.3	33.1
	LVL	7	2.2	2.2	35.3

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	ME	49	15.3	15.3	50.6
	VHE	93	29.1	29.1	79.7
	VLE	65	20.3	20.3	100.0
	Total	320	100.0	100.0	

VAR00006

		Frequency	percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	HE	95	29.7	29.7	29.7
	LE	50	15.6	15.6	45.3
	ME	104	32.5	32.5	77.8
	VHE	40	12.5	12.5	90.3
	VL	4	1.3	1.3	91.6
	VLE	27	8.4	8.4	100.0
	Total	320	100.0	100.0	

VAR00007

		Frequency	percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	HE	54	16.9	16.9	16.9
	LE	70	21.9	21.9	38.8
	ME	81	25.3	25.3	64.1
	VHE	57	17.8	17.8	81.9
	VL	30	9.4	9.4	91.3
	VLE	28	8.8	8.8	100.0
	Total	320	100.0	100.0	

VAR00008

		Frequency	percentage	Valid percentage	Cumulative percentage
Valid	HE	104	32.5	32.5	32.5
	LE	60	18.8	18.8	51.2
	ME	58	18.1	18.1	69.4
	VHE	53	16.6	16.6	85.9
	VLE	45	14.1	14.1	100.0
	Total	320	100.0	100.0	

PARTIAL CORR

/VARIABLES=VAR00003 VAR00004 VAR00005 VAR00006 VAR00007 VAR00008 VAR00002 BY VAR00001

/SIGNIFICANCE=TWOTAIL

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/STATISTICS=DERSCRIPTIVES

/MISSING =LISTWISE

Partial Correlation

Notes

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Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
VAR00001	3.6293	1.29045	321
VAR00002	3.6168	1.18568	321
VAR00003	3.6885	1.20526	321
VAR00004	3.1745	1.28237	321
VAR00005	3.4579	1.21409	321
VAR00006	3.7632	1.25251	321
VAR00007	3.5421	1.21151	321
VAR00008	3.0498	1.22882	321

Control Variables			VAR0000	VAR0000	VAR0000	VAR0000	VAR00005
			1	2	3	4	
VAR0000	VAR0000	Correlation	1.000	.981	.677	.473	-.197
1	1	Significance (2-tailed)	.000	.081	.000	.000	.000
		Df	0	318	318	318	318
	VAR0000	Correlation	.981	1.000	.433	.015	.629
	2	Significance (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.788	.000	.000
		Df	318	0	318	318	318
		Correlation	.677	.433	1.000	-.005	.167

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3	VAR0000 Significance tailed)	(2-.000	.000	.	.932	.003
	Df	318	318	0	318	318
4	VAR0000 Correlation	.473	.015	-.005	1.000	-.232
	Significance tailed)	(2-.000	.788	.932	.	.000
	Df	318	318	318	0	318
5	VAR0000 Correlation	-.197	.629	.167	-.232	1.000
	Significance tailed)	(2-.000	.000	.003	.000	.
	Df	318	318	318	318	0

Discussion of the Findings

Following the correlation result presented in Table 6, the correlation coefficient. For the study showed a positive relationship between Niger Delta and the development of the region representing 77.8% of the population. It indicates empowerment of the Niger Delta people through the acquisition of requisite skills, which has significantly contributed to the development of the region, is 0.981 and the p-value is 0.001. As observed in table 7 the correlation result showed a coefficient of 0.677 and the p-value is 0.000, hence the major challenges hindering resource control struggle by the people is the role of the elites and stakeholders, they failed to tell the youths the truth instead encouraged them to take up fire arm in the struggle see the ideas of (Hunter, 1953 & Dahl, 1961), It was revealed in table 8, the correlation result showed a coefficient of 0.473 and the p-value is 0.000; sanctimonious approach of the government and order institutions at implementing the policy framework on the allocation and development of the Niger Delta Region. Egobueze et al (2021) stated "The principle of independence and co-ordinate jurisdiction of different tiers of government that is a prerequisite of federalism has substantially been eroded, thus, exacerbating various forms of revolts over resource control and struggle in the region".

Findings

1. The major challenge in the development of the Niger Delta region is corruption among elites and agencies.
2. Poor implementation of several policy frameworks enacted by the federal government in addressing NDR development issues.
3. The Niger Delta elites are not effectively involved by the resource control agitator in the region, thus making it seem like gangsterism demands form government institutions.
4. The government is not sincere at interfacing with the stakeholders of the region in striking a balance to quail the pressures of the youth in their resource control demand.

Conclusion

There is no gain in saying that the Niger Delta resource control struggle is not inimical to the development of the region, which is worsened by the complexity of contradictions orchestrated by the elites of the NDR. To avert the deteriorating state of development and reposition the Niger Delta people’s prosperous future, the activities of the institutional agencies and their legal framework should be reviewed with stringent clauses that will expunge the elite’s contradictions at impeding the region’s smooth development. This is because no meaningful progress will be achieved in the region if the miscreant elites, corrupt actors, or officials of the agencies are not dealt with seriously serve as a deterrent to others who may be nursing such dastard thought. Beyond true federalism as a

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panacea. For achieving resource control by the agitators, institutional challenges and elite conspiracy are the major factors that have great impediments to the success of resource control and regional development.

Recommendations

1. The agitators of the Niger Delta will be committed and Join hands with the spirited stakeholders of Southern Nigeria to Continue to mount pressure on their Northern counterparts to restructure Nigeria/
2. The government should employ superior argument and dialogue with the agitators of resource control so as to eschew conflict resolution mechanism and armed struggle to demand. For their legitimate rights.
3. In addition, the 'local' variant (committed ordinary citizens) group should begin to engage their ex-governors, current governors, senators, house of representatives, house of assembly men, political office holders, political appointees, political class. And ex-militants as a matter of urgency by holding them accountable for all the allocations collected so far for the development of the region.
4. Agitators of the resources control principle should continue to engage the elite's brothers to come to terms with realities on the ground in the region so that they can appreciate their plights.

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